

Factorials, Integers, and Factorial Theorems for Computing and Cryptography

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Abstract: This paper presents an innovative theorem using factorials, integers, and binomials and multinomials. The theorems and its results can be used as an application in computing and cryptography to develop algorithms like RSA algorithm and Elliptic Curve Cryptography.

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1. Introduction

Binomials, multinomials, and combinatorial techniques [1-13] are used as powerful tools in artificial intelligence and machine learning for data analysis and cybersecurity for protection of the computing systems, devices, networks, programs and data from cyber-attacks. Also, the nonnegative integers play a crucial role in factorial functions or factorials [1-13] for building the theorems that are used for algorithms and software development. The results of factorials and binomial coefficients are used as strong applications without any vulnerability in artificial intelligence and cybersecurity.

2. Theorems in Factorials

The factorial of a non-negative integer n , denoted by $n!$, is the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n .

For example, $7! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 \times 6 \times 7 = 5040$. Note that zero factorial is always one, that is, $0! = 1$.

Theorem: $(n^2)! = b(n!)^2$, where b & n are integers; $b \geq 1$; and $n \geq 0$.

Proof;

This theorem is proved by using the following binomial coefficient [1-13]:

$$\binom{n+r}{r} = \frac{(n+r)!}{r!n!} = a \Rightarrow (n+r)! = a \times n! \times r!, \text{ where } a \text{ is a positive integer.}$$

$$(n \times r)! = b \times n! \times r! \text{ since } (n \times r) \geq (n+r).$$

Let $r = n$. Then, $(n \times n)! = b \times n! \times n! \Rightarrow (n^2)! = b(n!)^2$, where b is a positive integer.

Hence, theorem is proved.

Corollary 1: $(n \times r)! = c \times n! \times r!$, where c & n are integers; $c \geq 1$; and $n \geq 0$.

Corollary 2: $(n^r)! = d(n!)^r$, where $d, n, & r$ are integers; $d, r \geq 1$; and $n \geq 0$.

Corollary 3: $\{(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)^s\}! = e \times \{(n_1 + n_2 + n_3 + \dots + n_k)!\}^s$, where $e, n_i, & s$ are integers; $e, s \geq 1$; and $n_i \geq 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$.

Corollary 4: $\{(n_1 \times n_2 \times n_3 \times \dots \times n_k)^s\}! = f \times \{(n_1 \times n_2 \times n_3 \times \dots \times n_k)!\}^s$, where $f, n_i, & s$ are integers; $f, s \geq 1$; and $n_i \geq 0$ for $i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, k$.

This idea can help to the researchers working in computing & cryptography for developing programs to solve the real-world problems.

3. Conclusion

In this article, a theorem and its corollaries have been introduced using factorials, integers, binomials, and multinomials [1-13]. The theorem and its corollaries refer to methodological advances which are useful for researchers working in computer science, computational science, and cryptography for developing algorithms and software to solve the most real life problems and meet today's challenges.

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